

EXPERIENCES OF USING WAGE SYSTEMS IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR USE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

The article analyzes the experience of using wage systems in developed countries, their specific features and types of "service evaluation".

Key words: employee salary, motivation, human resources, employee motivation

Extensive experience of using very different wage systems has been accumulated in foreign developed countries. Systems of individual countries the following characters with: in Sweden united the work fee, Pay for seniority and rationalization in Japan, productivity growth in Germany encourage, USA at – qualification for right Great in Britain – fee for individual contracts, in France – wage isolation, in Italy - characterized by collective and individual increases to the network tariff rate and increases related to the increase in the cost of living. At the same time, in all labor payment systems, there is a general focus on increasing production efficiency ¹⁷⁸.

In the incentive systems of developed countries with a market economy, two directions are used: to stimulate the growth of production indicators and to stimulate the increase in the quality of the labor force.

Systems that stimulate the growth of labor productivity occupy one of the main places among the systems aimed at stimulating the growth of production efficiency. For example, in the United Kingdom, the practice of concluding a performance agreement between the management of the enterprise and the trade unions representing the interests of the workers has been introduced. The essence of these contracts is that the income from the growth of labor productivity is divided between entrepreneurs and employees in the appropriate proportion. This is without directly increasing production costs allows to increase the salary ².

In Germany, collective agreements on raising tariffs are based on the prospects of labor productivity and price increases. Capitalist countries are

¹Кувшинов А. И. Теоретические основы мотивации труда работников сельскохозяйственных предприятий / А. И. Кувшинов // Известия Оренбургского государственного аграрного университета. 2012. № 6 (38). С. 214

²Божченко Ж. Мотивация и материальное стимулирование работников сельского хозяйства / Ж. Божченко // Ежемесячный науч-но-практический журнал «Формирование и оплата труда в сельском хозяйстве». 2012. № 7. С. 30.

gradually isolated from work come came out without the work of the right traditional from the forms are giving up. The reason is that, on the one hand, it is difficult to measure the personal contribution of an individual worker in the overall production process, and on the other hand, the tasks of encouraging cooperation within the labor team, their members' sense of responsibility for the quality of the product, and the ability to restructure come to the fore ³.

For example, in Sweden, the success of the return to production at the group level encourage and reward to the system accent given, in connection with this, the variable part of the salary of the enterprise common results with depends respectively increased the work and business forms of payment have lost their importance.

Mental pressure and work organization in the structure of wages in Germany, its quality, of equipment action to do according to liability such as factors are taken into account. This is due to the placement of occupations in the organization of work, such as flexible forms of wages, and a great emphasis on rewards for taking on additional responsibility .

In France, strict indexation has simply been abandoned, moving to wage regulation based on collective and individual productivity, but the minimum wage is still indexed. In the public interest, it is planned to link the wage fund with the economic results of the firm .

In France, the following forms of wages apply, based on the practice of isolation, which can be combined with each other:

- alone works for right to pay;
- guaranteed minimum (usually 80%). and the salary, which includes a variable part (about 20%, but it varies from 10 to 50%) ;
- qualification depends note done partial variable part while Sex or wages depending on the results of the work of the team and the achievements of the employee.

This form of wage segregation can apply to all types of additional benefits (from compensation for natural goods to receiving company shares). In the case of individualization of wages, its size depends not on the worker's condition, but on his personal contribution to production. The service system is also often used in the salary policy. This evaluation system is aimed at assigning wages to employees with the same qualifications, but with different performance indicators.

³Дульзон С. В. Зарубежный опыт прогнозирования форми-рования и использования трудовых ресурсов / С. В. Дульзон // Ежеме-сячный научно-практический журнал «Нормирование и оплата труда в сельском хозяйстве». 2012. № 10. С. 11.

This "service evaluation" is common in different countries. Factors evaluated by the worker can be production and personal. Workers services evaluation methods various: questionnaire, point evaluation and expert evaluation, grouping of workers according to the results of their work evaluation. Thus, Uzbekistan is located at the crossroads of the West and the East, and has absorbed Eastern values and established friendly relations with the Western world, not copying it, but adopting its own management theory and practice. It is necessary to choose a more suitable motivational model based on experience. This election should determine the country's development path for many years to come.

Employing employees is a long-term investment, and long-term motivation allows them to feel wanted giving only in the organization the work continuously developed and should not forget that it is possible only when the professional skills of the employee are improved.

According to the experience of the best western managers, those who interest and encourage employees to fulfill company tasks, to form a team of like-minded people will succeed. What has been said means that motivation of workers in modern production serves as the economic basis of high labor efficiency of all categories of employees.

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